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● **The first record of the genus *Dactylipalpus* Chapuis and the species *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis (Coleoptera; Curculionidae; Scolytinae) from China**

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Abstract: Scolytines specimens collected from Yunnan Province were examined. The genus *Dactylipalpus* Chapuis, 1869 and the species *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869 are newly recorded from China. Photographs and morphological characteristics are provided.

Keywords: bark beetle, diversity, taxonomy, Yunnan

● **中国新纪录属宽小蠹属和新纪录种窗胸宽小蠹（鞘翅目；象甲科；小蠹亚科）**

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摘要：通过检视采自云南的标本，记述小蠹亚科一个中国新纪录属：宽小蠹属 *Dactylipalpus* Chapuis, 1869 和一个中国新纪录种：窗胸宽小蠹 *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869，并提供其成虫形态描述和图片。

关键词：树皮小蠹，多样性，分类，云南

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● Introduction

The genus *Dactylipalpus* (Coleoptera; Curculionidae; Scolytinae; Hylesinini) was established by Chapuis with the species *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869 from Malacca and Sulawesi (Chapuis 1869). The genus *Dactylipalpus* is characterized by its notably large body size (6.0–14.0 mm) within the subfamily Scolytinae. Currently, eleven species are recognized, nine of which are limited to the African region, one of which is found only in the Oriental region (Philippines), and one of which is spread throughout the Australian, Oceanian and Pacific region (Bright 2021). Here we report *D. transversus* Chapuis as a new record to the Chinese fauna based on specimens collected in Yunnan Province. Images of the adult female are provided.

● Material and methods

Total length was measured from apex of the head to the apex of the elytra and width was measured at the widest point of the specimen. The pronotum was measured for both its length (from the apex to base) and its maximum width.

Specimens were collected in May 2024 by light traps. Examination and description were performed using a Zeiss stemi 508c stereomicroscope. Habitus images were taken with a Canon EOS R5 Mark II digital camera equipped with a Canon MP-E 65 mm lens, and the final images were stacked with Helicon Focus 8 software. All voucher specimens are deposited in the personal collection of the first author.

FIGURE 1. A pronotum of *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869 (female) B dorsal view of *Phloeoborus* sp. (female) C pronotum and head of *Phloeoborus* sp. (female, lateral view).

FIGURE 2. Habitus of *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869 (female): **A** dorsal view **B** lateral view **C** front **D** pronotum **E** declivity. (Scale bar: 1 mm).

● Taxonomy

Genus *Dactylipalpus* Chapuis, 1869 宽小蠹属 new national record to China

Type species: *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869

Diagnosis. The genus *Dactylipalpus* resembles *Phloeoborus* Erichson in its large body size (>5 mm). However, it can be easily distinguished by the following combination of characters: the antennal club lacks a suture, and female pronotum bears a median, transverse, slitlike mycangium on the anterior third. In contrast, the antennal club of *Phloeoborus* bears two sutures (often obscure) and female lacks a transverse pronotal mycangium but possesses a large mycangium ornamented with hairs on the proepisternum (Wood 1986) (Fig. 1).

Dactylipalpus transversus Chapuis, 1869 窗胸宽小蠹 new national record to China

Figs. 2, 3

Dactylipalpus transversus Chapuis, 1869: 12.

Specimens examined. CHINA, Yunnan Prov., Xishuangbanna Dai Autonomous Prefecture, Jinghong city, Jinuo Mts., Xiaopuxi Village (中国云南省西双版纳景洪市基诺山小普希村), 2♀, 28–V–2024, leg. Ze-Hao Ma; Yunnan Prov., Xishuangbanna Dai Autonomous Prefecture, Mengla County, Mengla Town, Bubang Village (中国云南省西双版纳勐腊县勐腊镇补蚌村), 1♀, 21–V–2024, leg. Ze-Hao Ma.

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from the other oriental species, *Dactylipalpus niger* Schedl, by its shorter pronotal groove, which is 0.28 times the median length of the pronotum (compared to 0.33 times in *D. niger*). It further differs in having uniseriate granules and setae on the declivital interstriae.

Redescription. Female. Length 8.9–9.5 mm (n=3), 1.93–1.95 times as long as wide; body color dark brown to black. **Head:** frons weakly convex, arcuately impressed just above epistoma; surface shining with rather abundant, coarse, impressed, shallow punctures, each bearing a semi-erect scale-like seta at its center; longitudinally impressed on the vertex. Eye approximately three times as long as wide, suboblong. Antennal club large, subpyriform, unmarked by sutures, finely pubescent. Funicle 6-segmented (excluding pedicel). **Pronotum:** 0.50–0.53 times as long as wide, subquadrate, slightly wider posteriorly. Anterior margin almost straight except for a medial emargination; posterior margin bisinuate; a deep, narrow, almost straight transverse groove 1/4 of distance from anterior margin and occupying about 0.28 times the median; surface with median third coarsely punctured, the punctures merge with each other to form rows, the granules larger and more abundant in lateral areas, becoming asperate in anterolateral areas. **Elytra:** 1.43–1.47 times as long as wide. 2.92–3.14 times as long as pronotum. Scutellum small, subtriangle, setose. Elytral base strongly procurved and elevated by a row of crenulations; sides almost straight and subparallel on basal 3/4, rather broadly rounded behind. Striae impressed, punctures moderate, deep, oval, separated by less half their diameter. Interstriae 3–5 times as wide as striae, slightly elevated, rugose, shining, closely granulate, about 2–3 ranks of confused granules on each interspace. Declivity steep, convex; striae impressed, punctures larger than those on disc; interstriae 1–3 much smaller and lower than those on disc, with granules and setae arranged in uniseriate rows.

Distribution. China (Yunnan), Australia, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Vietnam, New Guinea and the Solomon Is (Bright 2021).

Host plants. Polyphagous (Wood & Bright 1992).

Remarks. According to Beaver & Liu (2010), prior records showed that *Dactylipalpus transversus* was distributed in Taiwan Province; however, the corresponding specimen labels were probably manipulated, making the Taiwanese distribution data untrustworthy. Consequently, the species' occurrence in Taiwan was subsequently omitted from its distribution in later works (Bright 2014).

FIGURE 3. Habitus of *Dactylipalpus transversus* Chapuis, 1869, live female. (Photo by Ze-Hao Ma)

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● Additional information

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